

2024 TO 2025

CMIP Annual Report

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This report was authored by IPO Staff: Beth Dingley, Eleanor O'Rourke, Briony Turner, Paul Smith, and Daniel Ellis with contributions from the CMIP Panel, the WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel, and Task Team co-leads.

Foreword

The last year has been an incredibly busy time for CMIP with planning for the next phase, CMIP7, ramping up significantly, and discussions regarding the longer-term vision of CMIP evolving.

The CMIP Panel, led by Helene Hewitt (Met Office, UK) and John Dunne (NOAA/GFDL, USA), have driven forward the design of the CMIP7 experimental structure culminating in the publication of the CMIP7 Overview Paper: An evolving Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 7 (CMIP7) and Fast Track in support of future climate assessment (Dunne et al., 2025).

Additionally, the work by the WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel (WIP) to develop the infrastructure, led by Paul Durack (PCMDI/LLNL, USA) and Matt Mizieliński (Met Office, UK), underpinning CMIP7 has ramped up significantly. Evolutions since CMIP6 are designed to enable easier reuse of the infrastructure between different CMIP phases and WCRP activities more widely. In addition, a WIP-led review of CMIP history was also published (Durack et al., 2025 GMD).

To compliment and aid the governance panels in their work, many task teams have delivered plans and recommendations for several key components required for CMIP. We mention just a few highlights here.

The full list of Task Teams and working groups and their outputs are available in the report.

The Data Request Task Team have delivered the CMIP7 Data Request, developed through large community engagement activity to assign variables to scientific opportunities, expanding the scope and accessibility of the Data Request while retaining and enhancing oversight of complex technical metadata. The Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) Task Team are also working hard to define, develop, and deliver the CVs for CMIP7. This includes developing a variable register, which will improve the consistency and transparency of data production for activities across WCRP. The Model Benchmarking Task Team released a Beta version of the Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF), utilising CMIP6 data, for community testing and feedback and have submitted a number of papers on both the REF and model benchmarking more widely. The Model Documentation Task Team have published their preliminary specifications for the 'Essential Model Documentation', which requires modelling centres to publish a subset of information about the model alongside the data to improve consistency in the availability of model documentation. The Forcings Task Team have delivered the majority of the CMIP7 DECK forcings suite, ready for modelling centres to run their Assessment Fast Track simulations.

They have also facilitated the delivery of an additional Population Density dataset which will aid the modelling of fire in the latest generation of Earth System Models. In January, we launched the new Energy Consumption and Carbon Footprint Task Team, who will evaluate the energy consumption and carbon footprint of CMIP, develop appropriate target setting and monitoring procedures, and identify potential actions for reducing the impact. Finally, the Strategic Ensemble Design Task Team delivered their recommendations on the experiment selection for the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track. With this delivery, the Strategic Ensemble Design Task Team has completed its objectives and was subsequently closed in December 2024. The Panel would like to thank the co-leads Isla Simpson (NCAR, US) and Ben Sanderson (CICERO, Norway) and members of the Task Team for their invaluable contribution.

Together, the CMIP Panel, the CMIP IPO, the Task Teams, and the WIP are working to deliver a suite of papers outlining the work achieved across the next year,

including papers outlining the Data Request, Rapid Evaluation Framework, Forcings, Variable Registry, and early plans for a CMIP Sustained Mode.

The IPO provides a key CMIP organisational hub, supporting the scientific and technical experts, and ensuring effective communication and facilitation across our broad and expanding international community.

The Fresh Eyes on CMIP working group of early career researchers, scientists, and practitioners, has spent the past year continuing work across numerous projects to aid users of CMIP data. Their work was shared globally during their inaugural workshop: Fresh Eyes on CMIP Around the World. The CMIP Panel and WIP are incredibly supportive of all the important work the Fresh Eyes community is performing and are excited to see the outputs benefit CMIP users in the years to come.

We look forward to continuing to work with the community in the year ahead!

The CMIP leadership

John Dunne
CMIP Panel Co-chair

Helene Hewitt
CMIP Panel Co-chair

Paul Durack
WIP Co-chair

Matt Mizielski
WIP Co-chair

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1 Governance and Operations

1.1 The CMIP Panel

The CMIP Panel is a World Climate Research Program (WCRP) Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM) subcommittee charged with overseeing the evolving design of Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) and with coordinating the various activities contributing to the science and impact of CMIP. The Panel provides recommendations, proposals, and insight to the WCRP Earth System Modelling and Observations (ESMO) Scientific Steering Group (SSG). The Panel works to empower modelling centres to deliver globally coordinated multi-model ensembles to further understanding of the climate system and provide foundations for climate mitigation and adaptation policy. The Panel promotes a transparent and open process to ensure equality of access to the process and of input to requirements and design choices. The CMIP Panel is made up of a Core Panel of up to eight members, who represent the decision-making body, together with an Extended Panel including all the co-leads of active task teams. The CMIP Panel is currently co-chaired by Helene Hewitt (Met Office, UK) and John Dunne (GFDL/NOAA, US). Ex-officio members provide links to the WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel (WIP), ESMO, Fresh Eyes on CMIP, ScenarioMIP, CORDEX and VIACS while emeritus members contribute their invaluable knowledge and experience.

In 2024 the Panel bid farewell to Core Panel member Olivier Boucher following a two-year term on Panel, where he advocated for carbon efficiency in the CMIP activities, and was a key member in setting up the new Energy Consumption and Carbon Footprint Task Team. The Panel would like to thank Olivier for his work while on the CMIP Panel. Following an open call for a new member to fill Olivier's position, the Panel were delighted to welcome Masa Kageyama (IPSL, France) to the Core Panel. Her experience in climate modelling, and especially in paleoclimate through her involvement in PMIP, will be a great asset to the Panel's work.

The evolution of the Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM) within the ESMO Core Project, has led to a change in the reporting structure of the CMIP Panel and WIP, who both now report directly to the ESMO Scientific Steering Group (ESMO SSG). The CMIP Panel now welcomes two Ex-Officio liaison members from the ESMO SSG, Roland Séférian (CNRM, France) and Michio Kawamiya (JAMSTEC, Japan).

Over the last year the Core Panel have been focused on the drafting, submission and responding to reviews of the CMIP7 overview paper (Dunne et al., 2025). An important element of the paper drafting was the evolution of four fundamental research questions motivating the coupled model intercomparison, which the data from CMIP7 will help to address substantially (for details see [Spotlight on CMIP7 and beyond](#)).

In April 2025, following the first round of reviews on the [CMIP7 Overview Paper](#), the CMIP Panel have decided to update the name of the upcoming Fast Track from 'AR7 Fast Track' to 'Assessment Fast Track'. The new name, Assessment Fast Track ([CMIP7 AFT](#)), reflects the AFT's utility to a broader range of assessments. Projected climate change in coupled models due to increased greenhouse gas concentrations has been part of every [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change \(IPCC\) report](#) since its inception and CMIP projections are now [used extensively in national and regional climate change assessments](#) supporting risk analysis, impact and adaptation planning. Additionally, the new name and acronym avoid embedded acronyms, providing clarity for our community.

In addition, the CMIP Panel has continued to provide feedback and approvals for key components of the CMIP7 delivery, while carefully monitoring progress and determining the impacts of delays on the CMIP7 AFT timeline. With approval of the IPCC AR7 timeline still pending, uncertainty remains around definitive deadlines requiring a continued dynamic approach and close collaboration with the WIP and partner activities/ organisations.

Looking forward, the CMIP Panel members will increasingly focus on facilitating the analysis of the CMIP7 AFT data as it starts to emerge in late 2025 and throughout 2026. The [CMIP Community Workshop 2026](#) in March next year will be a target and catalyst for this community co-created activity. With a number of task teams likely to fulfil their objectives over 2025–2026 the Panel will be carefully reviewing recommendations for transition to more permanent structures for key components such as climate forcings, data request and the Rapid Evaluation Framework.

CMIP Core Panel

Name	Affiliation	Country	Term	Role
John Dunne	NOAA-GFDL	USA	2023–	Co-chair
Helene Hewitt	Met Office	UK	2022–	Co-chair
Julie Arblaster	Monash University	Australia	2020–	Member
Frédéric Bonou	IRHOB/UNSTIM	Benin	2024–	Member
Tereza Cavazos	CICESE	Mexico	2024–	Member
Masa Kageyama	IPSL	France	2025–	Member
Tomoki Miyakawa	University of Tokyo	Japan	2023–	Member
Robert Pincus	LDEO/Columbia University	USA	2020–	Member
Paul Durack	PCMDI/LLNL	USA	2020–	Ex-Officio (WIP)
Matthew Mizielinski	Met Office	UK	2020–	Ex-Officio (WIP)
Michio Kawamiya	JAMSTEC	Japan	2025–	Ex-Officio (ESMO)
Roland Séférian	CNRM	France	2025–	Ex-Officio (ESMO)
Karl Taylor	PCMDI/LLNL	USA	2008–	Emeritus

Members departing in the past year

Name	Affiliation	Country	Term	Role
Olivier Boucher	IPSL	France	2023–2025	Member
Gregory Flato	CCCma	Canada	2016–2025	Ex-Officio (WGCM)

The CMIP Panel Co-chairs would like to thank both Olivier and Gregory for their contributions across their terms on the CMIP Panel.

CMIP Extended Panel

In addition to the CMIP Core Panel members, the following members make up the CMIP Extended Panel

Name	Affiliation	Country	Term	Role
Vaishali Naik	NOAA-GFDL	USA	2022–	Climate Forcings Co-lead
Zebedee Nicholls	Climate Resource / IIASA	Austria / Australia	2024–	Climate Forcings Co-lead
Atef Ben Nassar	IPSL	France	2023–	Data Access Co-lead
James Anstey	CCCma	Canada	2024–	Data Request Co-lead
Martin Jukes	STFC	UK	2022–	Data Request Co-lead
Chloe Mackallah	CSIRO	Australia	2022–	Data Request Co-lead
Birgit Hassler	DLR	Germany	2022–	Model Benchmarking Co-lead
Forrest Hoffman	ORNL	USA	2022–	Model Benchmarking Co-lead
Ranjini Swaminathan	University of Reading	UK	2024–	Model Benchmarking Co-lead
David Hassell	NCAS	UK	2022–	Model Documentation Co-lead
Charlotte Pascoe	CEDA	UK	2024–	Model Documentation Co-lead
Douglas Rao	NC State	USA	2023–	Fresh Eyes on CMIP Co-lead
Julia Mindlin	Leipzig University	Germany	2023–	Fresh Eyes on CMIP Co-lead
Silvina Solman	University of Buenos Aires	Argentina	2024–	Ex-Officio (CORDEX)
Claas Teichmann	GERICS	Germany	2023–	Ex-Officio (VIACS AB)
Detlef van Vuuren	Utrecht University	Netherlands	2023–	Ex-Officio (ScenarioMIP)

Members departing in the past year

Name	Affiliation	Country	Term	Role
Ben Sanderson	CICERO	Norway	2022–2024	Strategic Ensemble Design Co-lead
Isla Simpson	NSF NCAR	USA	2022–2024	Strategic Ensemble Design Co-lead
Guillaume Levavasseur	IPSL	France	2022–2024	Model Documentation Co-lead

The CMIP Panel Co-chairs would like to thank Ben, Isla, and Guillaume for their contributions across their terms on the CMIP Extended Panel.

Spotlight on... CMIP7 and beyond

Starting in early 2022, the [CMIP Panel](#) and [WIP](#), joined by the [CMIP Task Teams](#), have worked hard to evolve the structure of CMIP to address issues that were faced in [CMIP6](#). A range of [surveys](#) and [events](#) have taken place over the past three years to gather data on the successes and reflections from CMIP6. An often-raised challenge in CMIP6 was the high burden placed on the modelling centres from a large experiment list, frequently changed data request, and delays to historical forcing dataset provision. Further commentaries such as Jakob et al. (2023) and Stevens (2024) have highlighted the challenges seen by many of trying to meet both the needs of the climate research community and the increasing demand from climate services and policy users.

The CMIP projections are heavily relied upon in the [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change \(IPCC\)'s Assessment Reports](#) and other [national and international policy assessments](#). As such, previous CMIP phases have aligned themselves on the IPCC timelines, to ensure CMIP data and analysis are available for IPCC authors to synthesise in the latest report. Moving forwards, the CMIP Panel recognised that a change to the experimental design was needed to address the burden placed on modelling centres during CMIP6, while still targeting a data delivery timeline that serves the IPCC and other future climate assessments. Therefore, they proposed a more continuous approach for model intercomparison along with a targeted CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track (AFT) set of experiment designed to set priorities for the running of simulations to align with the needs, and likely ambitious timeline, of the IPCC 7th assessment cycle (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Structure of Future CMIP. Published at doi: [10.5281/zenodo.16602075](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16602075).

The CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track

The CMIP fast tracks are designed as a compact set of experiments including the DECK and selected experiments from Community MIPs that will support specific needs. The CMIP7 AFT is intended to specifically deliver on the IPCC 7th assessment cycle timeline and is also intended to serve a wider range of national and international assessments. Community MIPs will continue to be supported by the CMIP infrastructure but are free to operate on their own timeline, although we understand that some modelling centres/groups may choose to align with the AR7 timeline regardless.

CMIP7 Overview Paper and fundamental research questions

Throughout the past year, CMIP Panel co-chair, John Dunne (NOAA/GFDL) has led the development of the CMIP7 Overview Paper manuscript: An evolving Coupled Model Intercomparison Project phase 7 (CMIP7) and Fast Track in support of future climate assessment. On 9 December 2024, this was submitted to GMD and began going through the peer review process. The final version of the manuscript should be accepted in mid-2025 and we hope it will be published as a GMD highlight paper.

An important element of the paper is the description of the four fundamental research questions which CMIP7, including the CMIP7 AFT, will seek to address:

1. **Patterns of sea surface change:** How will tropical ocean temperature patterns co-evolve with those at higher latitudes?
2. **Changing weather:** How will dangerous weather patterns evolve?
3. **Water-carbon-climate nexus:** How will Earth respond to human efforts to manage the carbon cycle?
4. **Tipping Points:** What are the risks of triggering irreversible changes across possible climate trajectories?

An updated set of climate scenarios

In January 2025, ScenarioMIP released their preprint (van Vuuren et al., 2025), outlining the set of climate scenarios designed for CMIP7. These scenarios were developed by ScenarioMIP and were widely consulted on in the climate and wider community. The original preprint features six different future climate scenarios:

- **High Emission Scenario (H):** High emission scenario to explore potential high-end impacts
- **Medium Emission Scenario (M):** Medium emission scenario consistent with current policies
- **Medium-Low Scenario (ML):** Scenario with delayed increase in mitigation effort, insufficient to meet Paris Agreement objectives

- **Low Emission Scenarios:** Includes three trajectories aligned with the Paris Agreement:
 - **A feasible Low (L)** scenario consistent with staying likely below 2 °C
 - **A Very Low with Limited Overshoot (VLLO)** consistent with limiting warming to 1.5°C by 2100 AD with limited overshoot (as low as plausible) of 1.5°C during the 21st century
 - **A Very Low after High Overshoot (VLHO)** scenario with similar end-of-century temperature impact to VLLO, but with less aggressive near-term mitigation and large reliance on net negative emissions, resulting in a higher overshoot.

Review responses are being currently being addressed by the ScenarioMIP community, which include a potential additional High-Low scenario and modifications of the extension scenarios beyond 2100.

A sustained mode CMIP

Following discussions in advance of, and during, the ESMO Kick Off meeting in March 2024 in Hamburg, a small working group made up of the chairs of the CMIP Panel, WIP and WGCM was formed to deliver a scoping document on potential for "service" elements of CMIP to be delivered in a more regular and sustained mode.

In the discussions that followed a clear need for more regular climate information was identified and two areas highlighted as tangible targets for regular and sustained delivery:

Figure 2: Illustration of a vision for a future CMIP structure with elements of CMIP delivery moving to annual (extended historical forcings) or five yearly (climate projections). Community MIPs, model and forcings development would feed into the "sustained mode" as a research to operations activity.

Annual historical forcings extensions: An important outcome of the Pathway to regular and sustained delivery of climate forcing datasets workshop was an ambition to prototype provision of annual extensions of the historical forcing datasets facilitating up to date historical simulations to understand recent climate and serve many other user groups. This vision is described in an upcoming Nature Commentary piece, led by Forcings Task Team co-lead Vaishali Naik (NOAA/GFDL, US), highlighting four areas of action required to deliver this ambition and some first steps. These initial steps include pursuing a WMO mandate encouraging members to support the consistent and timely delivery of annual extensions of earth system forcing data, and evolution of the CMIP Forcings Task Team into a Forcings Panel under ESMO supporting continued collaborative forcings science research and development.

Five yearly climate projections: CMIP has traditionally aligned with IPCC timelines which are non-uniform and often agreed well into the cycle resulting in uncertainty and large burden on the CMIP community to prepare and deliver. The more stable five-year cycle of the Global Stocktake would allow modelling centres to plan their model development and for streamlining of global->regional->impacts climate information chain.

Led by Helene Hewitt (UK Met Office), CMIP Panel Co-Chair, the Towards provision of regularly updated climate data from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (Hewitt et al., in preparation) manuscript outlines this sustained and regular delivery mode vision, with publication expected in late 2025.

1.2 The WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel

The objective of the WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel (WIP) is to provide guidance and oversee infrastructure development so that it will be fit for its purpose and meet the scientific needs of CMIP and other MIP projects. The mission of the WIP is to promote a robust and sustainable global data infrastructure to support a number of projects within WCRP. The WIP is co-chaired by Paul Durack (PCMDI / LLNL, USA) and Matthew Mizielinski (Met Office, UK).

Over the past year membership of the WIP has undergone some reorganisation with four new members, Guillaume Levavasseur (IPSL, France), Mario Acosta (BSC, Spain), Charlotte Pascoe (CEDA, UK) and Zebedee Nicholls (Climate Resource/IIASA, Austria), recruited through an [open call in November 2024](#) to the WIP Core Panel. The WIP Extended Panel, similar to the CMIP Extended Panel, includes all WIP task team co-leads and stakeholders.

CMIP7 infrastructure development has accelerated over 2024 to 2025. The Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) Task Team was established in March 2025, recognising the need for a specific group to lead CVs development. The CMIP7 CVs will anchor many of the downstream infrastructure services relied on by modelling groups in, for example, generating output conforming to CMIP standards (e.g. CMIP7 Data Request, Essential Model Documentation, CMOR and other data preparation tools) and enabling the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) publisher to index and serve the datasets.

To maximise resources available to the CMIP7 infrastructure development, the [ESGF CMIP6 project was closed in April 2025 \(Mizielinski et al; 2025\)](#). The community has been able to utilise CMIP6Plus to continue publication of CMIP6 DECK like and MIP data and importantly CMIP6Plus has provided a platform for the testing versions of the CMIP7 DECK forcings datasets.

A new development for CMIP7 will be the introduction of a variable registry that will be co-managed as a community resource and will host the metadata needed to uniquely define variables that might be requested from MIP experiments, observations, and other ancillary MIP data products (e.g., forcing datasets). Alongside the registry will be the introduction of “branded variable” name, constructed from a root name associated with the standard name defining the property, and a branding suffix, which indicates how the property should be sampled spatially and temporally.

This development has been implemented to improve consistency, provenance, and identification of data for users.

The CMIP7 infrastructure is anticipated to be testing ready in September 2025, which, together with the delivered CMIP7 Data Request and Essential Model Documentation (EMD), will allow modelling centres to prepare their publishing workflows.

The ESGF, an open-source effort providing a robust, distributed data platform, enables worldwide access to CMIP, CORDEX, input4MIPs, and obs4MIPs data, and is finalising the implementation of their ESGF-Next Generation system. This new system introduces a cloud ready deployment architecture a new system for distributed search. The WIP and ESGF Executive Committee (ESGF XC) have been working closely to ensure both the ESGF and CMIP7 infrastructure will be in place ready for the first CMIP7 data expected towards the end of 2025. Together with the Climate Data Node Operations Team (CDNOT) and the CMIP IPO there have also been efforts to strengthen the resilience of the ESGF, particularly against a changing geopolitical landscape.

A node survey was launched in February 2025 to identify any nodes that are no longer active, determining the planned storage available for CMIP7 and CORDEX, and identifying where additional funding is envisioned or support to garner funding is required. These efforts will continue into 2026 with particular focus on increasing participation from nodes outside Europe and the USA.

Looking forward the WIP goals for the upcoming year are:

- Finalise the implementation of the CMIP7 CVs and rollout to community.
- Provide up to date guidance to support utilisation of the CMIP7 infrastructure firstly focused on modelling centres and then to the wider user community.
- Launch of the variable registry, publication of the associated peer reviewed paper and community communication on the registry and "branded variables".
- Facilitate registration of models planning to submit CMIP7 data.
- Support increasing ESGF's resilience and expansion of participating nodes, particularly in currently under-represented regions,
- Facilitate and support publication of the CMIP7 AFT and CORDEX-CMIP6 data.

WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Core Panel members

Name	Affiliation	Country	Term	Role
Paul Durack	PCMDI / LLNL	USA	2017–	Co-chair, 2021–
Matthew Mizielinski	Met Office	UK	2018–	Co-chair, 2020–
Mario Acosta	BSC	Spain	2024–	Member
Sasha Ames	LLNL	USA	2019–	Member
David Hassell	NCAS	UK	2019–	Member
Martin Jukes	STFC	UK	2014–	Member
David Hassell	NCAS	UK	2019–	Member
Guillaume Levavasseur	IPSL	France	2024–	Member
Zebedee Nicholls	Climate Resource / IIASA	Austria	2024–	Member
Charlotte Pascoe	CEDA	UK	2024–	Member
Karl Taylor	PCMDI/LLNL	USA	2014–	Member
Alison Cobb	ECMWF	UK	2025–	Ex-Officio (ESMO)
Forrest Hoffman	ORNL	US	2024–	Ex-Officio (ESGF)
Philip Kershaw	STFC	UK	2024–	Ex-Officio (ESGF)
Juliette Lavoie	OURANOS	Canada	2024–	Ex-Officio (Fresh Eyes on CMIP)
Elisa Ziegler	University of Tübingen	Germany	2025–	Ex-Officio (Fresh Eyes on CMIP)

Members departing in the past year

Name	Affiliation	Country	Term	Role
Yuqi Bai	Tsinghua University	China	2018–2024	Member
Slava Kharin	CCCma	Canada	2014–2024	Member
Grigory Nikulin	SMHI	Sweden	2021–2024	Member
Andrea Lammert	DKRZ	Germany	2021–2024	Member

WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Extended Panel and Stakeholder Panel members

Name	Affiliation	Country	Term	Role
Martina Stockhause	DKRZ	Germany	2019–	Stakeholder - IPCC DDC & TG Data
Andrea Lammert	DKRZ	Germany	2021–	Stakeholder - DKRZ
Jesús Fernández	UNICAN	Spain	2024–	Stakeholder - CORDEX
Katharina Berger	DKRZ	Germany	2021–	Task Team co-lead - CDNOT
James Anstey	CCCma	Canada	2024–	Task Team co-lead - Data Request
Chloe Mackallah	CSIRO	Australia	2024–	Task Team co-lead - Data Request
Laurent Troussellier	IPSL	France	2024–	Task Team co-lead - CVs

Spotlight on... CMIP7 Infrastructure Development

Controlled Vocabularies

The core pieces of infrastructure development are the all closely connected to the metadata used within CMIP which are encoded within the Controlled Vocabularies (CVs). The structure of this is key to the operation of the CMORisation and ESGF infrastructure and is integrated into services such as ESG-VOC.

In building on CMIP6 infrastructure evolution we have concentrated on providing a more succinct and comprehensive description of the models and their components, whilst aiming to develop a scalable system that is easier to interact with (for modelling centres, reviewers and the general public).

Over the different CMIP eras, the complexity and quantity of data and simulations are increasing. Therefore, a distributed and linked system using JSON Linked-Data is being developed allowing better management, and uniformity between metadata submissions of control variables.

Key changes for CMIP7 are outlined below:

- Automation to reduce human error.
- Automatic checks for metadata conformance (e.g. permissible values, file formats, naming conventions).

- Reusable CV items (e.g. institution_id's which may be used across projects) are linked instead of copied, reducing duplication, and the need to update multiple sources.
- Familiar and web-standard JSON format similar to CMIP6, but with additional capabilities in the back end of the infrastructure.
- The separation of multi-entry files. This allows for more discrete content ownership, better change management and makes it easier to locate specific information. If something needs to be updated, the risk of something breaking is mitigated using this system.
- Github Forms allow a more user-friendly method to interact with the JSON source of the CVs. This includes automation of checks, providing feedback to the submitter and creating a framework, within which all new updates need to be reviewed before being submitted.
- Summary scripts – we can use the framing capabilities of JSON-LD to simplify the metadata to provide simplified or bespoke outputs for our different user communities.
- In using GitHub actions and Pages, we can also automate the generation of documentation for each part of the CVs. This means that as the data gets updated, so does the documentation describing it.

One benefit of this framework is that it can be expanded to other projects and tasks. For example, we are able to link results from the Essential Model Documentation and the forthcoming Variable Registry by storing the files in this format. This means that teams responsible for each item can manage and update the data, whilst still interacting with the WCRP-CMIP infrastructure.

ESGF Next Generation infrastructure development

Since 2020, the ESGF community has been re-engineering the infrastructure that delivers projects such as CMIP. This “Next Generation” infrastructure (ESGF-NG) will replace all existing CMIP services and is vital for several reasons:

1. To allow new technologies to be used to support data publication and distribution.
2. To allow old software libraries and systems to be retired, as support for and maintaining security of various individual components is becoming difficult.
3. To enable the inter-operation of ESGF with a range of other services.

The ESGF-NG architecture is expected to be operational from September 2025. As part of the move to NG, there will be a change to node hierarchy, with an east and west node mirroring all holdings for CMIP, input4MIPs, obs4MIPs and CORDEX data, at around 75–80 PB. Regional nodes will continue to publish, replicate and provide data access via online methods such as Globus and Kerchunk, but will not replicate the entire data stack. To ensure resilience, the CMIP IPO are connecting with external agencies such as the WMO to find institutions interested in supporting the work of ESGF and provide data storage and access of important climate data sets such as CMIP.

1.3 CMIP International Project Office

The CMIP IPO is hosted by ESA's Climate Office at its European Centre for Space Applications and Telecommunications (ECSAT) facility in Oxfordshire, United Kingdom. During the 2024 to 2025 period, the IPO welcomed a new team member, Paul Smith. Paul joins the IPO as a Science and Infrastructure Facilitation Officer, bringing experience from a varied career, including time as a Station Manager in the Integrated Carbon Observing System (ICOS) community. Between 20 January and 11 April 2025, the IPO also welcomed Dóra Hegedűs on a three-month seconded placement from the UK's Science and Technology Research Council. Dóra worked with the Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF) delivery team and obs4MIPs on ensuring suitable provenance records and citation information are included in the REF.

The IPO is run by staff from HE Space Operations under contract to ESA.

The role of the CMIP IPO is to:

- Provide coordination and organisational support of the activities of the CMIP Panel and WIP, including relevant sessions, meetings, workshops, conferences, and training sessions.
- Support coordination, planning, development, and implementation of the CMIP experimental design, data archiving and dissemination, and associated observational reanalysis, forcings, scenarios and modelling efforts.
- Facilitate international coordination and communication with related WCRP and other international programmes as well as active liaison between the climate observations and modelling communities.
- Identify and scope funding requirements supporting CMIP delivery through regular engagement with current and potential funders, supporting community participation in national and regional funding programmes, and providing direct funding and resource, as available, to support priority workstreams.
- Prepare reports, correspondence, and publications.
- Coordinate CMIP scientific communication, dissemination, and outreach.

The CMIP IPO also collaborates closely with related WCRP, other international programmes, funding agencies and wider stakeholders. Figure 3 shows the CMIP IPO's position within the broader WCRP landscape.

“ The CMIP-IPO continues to facilitate the CMIP community as they prepare to deliver the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track, which will contribute to the IPCC Assessment Report 7, and wider CMIP7 activities. This structured and systematic support has been hugely appreciated by the climate modelling community and represents a major step forward. The CMIP-IPO's activities have also helped to inter-link with European and international climate modelling activities, with a notable link to the Copernicus Climate Change Service and the European Union. A major advance was increased structural support for the systematic provision of CMIP historical forcing data ensuring more timely delivery. Another very positive aspect is the very pro-active involvement of early career researchers in the CMIP activities. ”

Susanne Mecklenburg, Head of Climate & Long-Term Action Division, ESA

Figure 3: The CMIP International Project Office within the wider WCRP landscape. Boxes outlined in yellow indicate groups/activities the IPO provide secretariat support for. Boxes outlined in blue indicate groups/activities the IPO engages with to aid the CMIP Community.

IPO Staff

Eleanor O'Rourke
Director

Briony Turner
Programme Manager

Beth Dingley
Science and
Communications Officer

Daniel Ellis
Technical Officer

Paul Smith
Science and Infrastructure
Facilitation Officer

Alice Kolesnikov,
Part-time Administrative
Support

Christopher Goddard
Part-time C3S-CMIP
Liaison Officer

1.4 Travel support fund

The Travel Support Fund has been running since August 2023 and is designed to help the CMIP Community attend CMIP-relevant conferences and meetings to boost networking and collaboration. The Travel Support Fund was initially launched exclusively to our Fresh Eyes on CMIP community, to help early career scientists attend meetings which could have a large impact on their future career. The fund was subsequently extended to Task Team members for attendance at Task Team specific meetings, or in other exceptional circumstances. The CMIP IPO reviews applications on a rolling basis as they arrive and accepts/rejects based on availability of funds.

In the past year, the Travel Support Fund has supported 18 members of the community across ten different events, including AGU, EGU, and ESA's Living Planet Symposium. CMIP has an ongoing mission to widen participation and encourage diversity across the community. In line with this, of the 19 recipients of the fund, 10 are early career scientists, 11 are women, and two are working in the Global South.

1.5 Carbon footprint

CMIP is an accumulation of international scientific effort. This includes a multitude of activities that have an emissions footprint, such as from computing and meeting travel. The science of CMIP is important, but we must be conscious of the carbon footprint this work is associated with. WCRP has committed to reducing its carbon footprint across all activities. Within the CMIP community, we are focusing on four key areas of reduction:

- eliminate unnecessary data duplication,
- network and data transmission optimisation,
- intentional decision making on CMIP design (experiments, computation, and storage),
- activities of the CMIP community (Scope 3 emissions).

This work is ramping up with the recent launch of the Energy Consumption and Carbon Footprint Task Team. Additionally, the CMIP IPO records an estimate of carbon emissions from all travel that is either:

1. Funded by the CMIP IPO (including IPO staff and community members receiving funding via the Travel Support Fund),
2. CMIP Community members attending a conference/meeting on behalf of their CMIP affiliation (e.g. a CMIP Panel member attending a meeting to represent the CMIP Panel),
3. Attendance at a CMIP IPO organised/facilitated event.

Between July 2024 and July 2025, the total carbon emissions from CMIP travel were 39,288 kgCO₂e. Of this, the emissions from IPO funded travel (including IPO staff travel) were 21,452 kgCO₂e. IPO staff travel accounted for 509 kgCO₂e. Compared with the same period the previous year, carbon emissions from travel were reduced by 58% for 2024–2025. With planning for the CMIP Community Workshop 2026 underway, to be held in Kyoto, Japan in March 2026, we anticipate higher emissions next year. Therefore, the IPO made a conscious effort to minimise emissions for this reporting period including choosing rail over flights when travelling within Europe.

CMIP across the globe

Our year in numbers

1 New CMIP Panel member

5 Full time IPO staff members

4 New WIP members

8 Active Task Teams
1 Task Team closed

45 countries

Where we have CMIP Activity members

28 countries

Have contributed to modelling or data infrastructure

€20,868

To support CMIP Community attend conferences and meetings

28% to support members from the Global South

7

Events facilitated by our IPO across different meetings / conferences

8

Virtual drop-in sessions for the community

528

CMIP Internal Community members

37

YouTube videos published

100%

Increase in LinkedIn followers

20,240

Post impressions on LinkedIn

20% increase in impressions

2140

Followers on new Bluesky account

9 seminars

Held in our CMIP Seminar series

35 publications

On CMIP Zenodo Community

15,316 datasets

Published to CMIP6 on ESGF

39,288 kgCO₂e

Emissions from travel

58% reduction in carbon emissions since last year

2 CMIP Community

The CMIP Community is a thriving, diverse community which continuously drives forward the innovation, design, and impact of CMIP. The CMIP Community is comprised of task teams, working groups, and the Fresh Eyes on CMIP early career scientists' initiative. Members of these communities represent academia, government, and the private sector to ensure that CMIP's outputs serve all industries and uses who need them.

The overarching objectives the CMIP Community work towards are to:

1. Increase CMIP's scientific and societal relevance,
2. Improve accessibility and widen participation,
3. Support the design, scope, and definition of the next phase of CMIP,
4. Support the evolution of CMIP infrastructure and future operationalisation.

2.1 Data Request Task Team

The focus of the [Data Request Task Team](#) is to oversee the creation of the CMIP7 Data Request. The Data Request has worked tirelessly over the past year to provide participating modelling centres with full details of CMIP7 output requirements, through engagement with the scientific community, helping to ensure that the CMIP7 output requirements accurately reflect the ambition of the latest scientific requirements, the constraints of the data managing services, and the resources of the modelling centres.

Throughout the past year, the Task Team implemented a large community engagement activity to develop the list of variables for CMIP7, including identifying the scientific objectives of groups of variables, experiments which are required to complete these objectives, and scrutinising the technical definition of the required variables. For this, the Task Team have worked in collaboration with five thematic author teams, covering the key domains of climate data producers and users. This has led to the release of number of versions of the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track Data Request. The latest major version, v1.2 can be used by modelling centres for model configuration in preparation for running AFT simulations. Subsequent minor releases, the [latest being v1.2.2](#), provide technical updates to a small number of variables to improve consistency across the request.

In addition to the technical preparation of the request, the Task Team and thematic author teams have also written up their work in a series of papers, submitted to the [GMD CMIP7 Special Issue](#).

Simultaneously to the development of the request content, a subgroup of the Task Team, the [Technical Implementation Subgroup \(TISG\)](#), have developed an API to allow for programmatic access to the Data Request content. This will aid modelling centres in exploring and implementing the request into their workflows.

Read more about Data Request development, in its dedicated [Spotlight on CMIP7 Data Request development, public consultation, and release](#) section below.

Looking ahead, with the majority of the work to create the CMIP7 AFT Data Request complete, the Task Team will shift its focus to developing recommendations on how future harmonised and unharmonised Data Requests could work in the CMIP ecosystem. Alongside this, the TISG will continue development of the Data Request API, including integrating the API with the upcoming CMIP7 CVs and Variable Register.

The Data Request Task Team is co-led by Martin Jukes (STFC, UK), Chloe Mackallah (CSIRO, Australia), and James Anstey (CCCma, Canada). Additionally, the TISG of the Data Request is co-lead by James and Marie-Pierre Moine (CERFACS, France). Full Task Team membership is [available on their website](#):

Spotlight on... CMIP7 Data Request development, public consultation, and release

In an analysis of the [CMIP6 Survey](#), most users found the CMIP6 Data Request to be too complex with too little documentation. However, the value in a consistent Data Request was also commonly reported. The survey also found significant tensions, including:

- Data users wanting more variables but data producers struggling with the size of request, and
- Those wanting fewer updates to the Data Request with others wanting more regular version releases.

Thematic author teams and public consultation

Across the past year, five thematic author teams have coordinated their scientific communities, to gather data requirements in the form of Opportunities, Variable Groups, Variables, and Physical Parameters. This has resulted in a collection of harmonised variables to support the high impact analysis of climate model output and provide a consistent and robust set of parameters on which to build the CMIP7 archive. The Data Request includes variable definitions and the mapping of variables. This has ensured that the Data Request balances scientific demand for data against modelling centre and infrastructure capacity.

This process for developing the Data Request was designed to enable a more transparent and effective approach to variable and request harmonisation and prioritisation. The five themes were:

- [Impacts & adaptation](#)
- [Ocean & sea-ice](#)
- [Atmosphere](#)
- [Earth system](#)
- [Land & land-ice](#)

The public consultation was organised across three phases. The first (5 August-18 October 2024) gathered the key content of the Data Request. This was started by asking the community to identify the scientific opportunities they wanted the CMIP7 archive to help answer on the AFT timeline. From the gathered Opportunities, variable lists and definitions were collected to create the [**first release of the CMIP7 Data Request**](#) (v1.0) on 22 November 2024. This release [**contained**](#) 48 Opportunities, 182 Variable Groups, 1813 variable, linked to 39 experiments.

In the second phase of consultation (6 December 2024 – 17 January 2025), significant review of the content in v1.0 was undertaken. This review was targeted to a) spot gaps in the v1.0 release, either in the scientific objectives (Opportunities) or the variables requested to answer those objectives, b) identify technical errors in the content, and c) receive feedback from modelling centres and MIPs on the request.

The [**second version of the CMIP7 Data Request**](#), v1.1, was released on 30 January and [**contained**](#) 28 Opportunities, 193 Variable Groups, 1820 variables, linked to 39 experiments.

The goals of the third and final phase of public consultation (30 January – 17 March 2025) was to ensure that v1.2 of the CMIP7 Data Request was stable and complete, allowing modelling centres to start their CMIP7 simulations. During this phase, a systematic variable review was undertaken to review the technical description of each variable included in the request. Due to the complexity of this task, the v1.2, originally planned to be the final release, was instead released with one subsequent technical updates, [**v1.2 \(released 1 April 2025\)**](#), [**v1.2.1 \(released 26 April 2025\)**](#) and two additional updates planned for Q3 of 2025.

The work done by the Task Team and thematic author teams has been summarised in a series of papers, submitted to GMD. The papers should be published in late 2025 / early 2026 for the community to read and reference as they start producing and using CMIP7 data.

2.2 Forcings Task Team

Over the last year, the Forcings Task Team has grown to 18 members and seven stakeholders with an additional co-lead, Zebedee Nicholls (Climate Resource/IIASA, Austria), joining Paul Durack (PCMDI/LLNL, USA) and Vaishali Naik (NOAA/GFDL, USA) in October 2024. This increase in committed resource is a reflection of the huge demand placed on the Task Team. Responding to the feedback on delayed forcing data provision during CMIP6, the Forcings Task Team have continued to work hard to ensure timely delivery of a well-tested and evaluated suite of datasets to support the CMIP7 AFT and wider CMIP7 activities. The Task Team is focused on the delivering forcings for the DECK experiments. See more details on the [CMIP7 Forcings webpage](#).

The first versions of these datasets were made available in late 2024, allowing for testing by the modelling centres and active feedback through [dedicated Github discussions](#). This process was intended to address any issues before the frozen CMIP7 DECK datasets were finalised in early 2025. The team set an ambitious deadline for delivery at end of February 2025, which was achieved by more than half of dataset providers. Due to their dependence on other forcing datasets, and a required correction to the stratospheric volcanic SO₂ emissions dataset, ozone concentrations and nitrogen deposition (only required for those models without interactive aerosol) are expected in August 2025.

The custom forcing datasets required by CMIP7 AFT experiments beyond the DECK are the responsibility of the relevant MIPs. However, the Task Team are keen to support publication of this data into the [input4MIPs ESGF project](#), provide access to relevant tools, and ensure links to the data and associated documentation are made clearly available on the CMIP website. They further welcome contributions of forcing datasets required by community MIP experiments, and prototype or alternative datasets not currently included in the standard CMIP DECK forcing suite, provided they conform to CMIP data formats. An exciting example of a community developed dataset is [population density](#), which was highlighted as a critical requirement for those models with interactive fire.

Following the delivery of the historical forcings, the Task Team shifting their focus onto developing the future scenario forcing and harmonisation of historical datasets and future scenarios, working closely with representatives of ScenarioMIP and the Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) community. Delivery of the first test versions of the scenario forcings is anticipated in September 2025.

Given the importance of these forcing datasets, and their wide use within and beyond CMIP, there has been considerable discussion both within the Task Team and with a range of partners and funders across the globe. The [Pathway to regular and sustained delivery of climate forcing datasets workshop](#), hosted by ECMWF in Reading in October 2025, accelerated these discussions and identified some key actions and next steps (see Section 4.1 for further event details). A key outcome was an ambition to deliver annual extensions to the historical forcings. This and other outcomes will be discussed in two published papers:

- Earth system forcing for CMIP7 and beyond (Durack et al, 2025), planned for submission to the Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society (BAMS) in July 2025.
- Climate models need more frequent releases of input data (Naik et al., 2025), planned for submission as a Nature Comment in August 2025.

Annual forcing dataset extensions will be a priority first step in the CMIP vision for more regular and sustained delivery of climate information (see [Spotlight on CMIP7 and beyond](#)).

The Forcings Task Team and Fresh Eyes projects have continued to be very active in engaging with the wider community over the last year with dedicated science sessions and involvement in CMIP townhalls at AGU24 and EGU25 including:

- AGU Fall Meeting 2024 session [Climate forcing: quantifying the roles and responses of anthropogenic and natural climate drivers](#)
- EGU Meeting 2025 session [Integrating Earth System Reconstructions and Climate Modeling: Forcing, Uncertainties, and Next-Generation Digital Twins](#)

The team members have also presented to interested institutions and projects throughout the year sharing the latest developments and plans for the CMIP7 forcing dataset delivery with community drop in sessions in October 2024 ([slides](#) and [recording](#)) and March 2025 ([slides](#) and [recording](#)). The [Forcings Task Team](#) and [CMIP7 Forcing Datasets webpages](#), including FAQs and the [input4MIPs Github](#) for dataset access, documentation and [feedback](#) are regularly updated. Publications can be found in the [Zenodo WCRP-CMIP Community](#). Finally, a [CMIP7 forcings and inputs – development, documentation, and evaluation](#) Geoscientific Model Development Special Issue has been established, which will bring together the peer-reviewed documentation papers associated with each forcing dataset.

The Forcings Task Team is co-led by Paul Durack (PCMDI/LLNL, USA), Vaishali Naik (GFDL/NOAA, USA) and Zebedee Nicholls (Climate Resource/IIASA, Austria). Full Task Team membership is [available on their website](#).

2.3 Model Benchmarking Task Team

The objectives of the Model Benchmarking Task Team were updated in December 2024 to reflect responsibility for implementation, and guiding initial community use, of the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF). The Task Team duration was extended for this by 18 months and Ranjini Swaminathan (University of Reading) was brought in as a third co-lead.

The REF is a new framework which will allow for model simulations to be rapidly evaluated by a range of existing climate metrics as the data are uploaded to ESGF. Evaluating climate models in this way allows for modelling centres to validate their model and allows users to assess and investigate the CMIP data. The CMIP6 and CMIP6 plus REF launch is planned for October 2025. Once the CMIP7 CVs are finalised and available, the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track REF will be finalised. The Task Team plans to launch this, with demonstrations using CMIP7 data from the Met Office and JAMSTEC at the CMIP Community Workshop in Kyoto in 2026.

The majority of the work to develop the REF has taken place over the past year. The Task Team's strategic approach for the REF was approved by the CMIP Panel in July 2024. The US Department of Energy and the European Space Agency have since provided resources for development of the Assessment Fast Track REF, supporting work by Climate Resource, ORNL, LLNL, and the Netherlands e-Science Centre.

In-kind time contributions have also been provided by staff from RAL-SPACE STFC, CEDA and the following model benchmarking packages: ILAMB, ESMValTool, PMP and IOMB. All parties are working to an agreed set of work packages set out in a collaboration agreement.

The Task Team has led on community engagement, running a hackathon, launching a Beta release of the REF and running four drop-in sessions to raise community awareness and input as well as sessions at AGU, EGU and ESA's Living Planet Symposium. They have provided requirements to the delivery team for the REF interface, worked to finalise the nomenclature of the diagnostics and continue to work with the joint WIP-ESGF working group on the best way to implement quality assurance/ quality control packages for CMIP data on ESGF.

The Task Team have also worked to finalise and submit two papers for peer review. The first is an invited paper in Reviews of Geophysics which reviews model benchmarking and evaluation tools and highlights the progress the community has made developing these approaches over the past decade. The second is a paper outlining the ambitious vision to develop a Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF) for CMIP7. The community engagement activities and the development process overseen by the Model Benchmarking Task Team co-leads.

Another paper the Task Team are preparing is an invited submission to the Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society (BAMS), which summarises the observational requirements for effective model benchmarking. Finally, the Task Team is preparing a paper outlining new perspectives for model benchmarking and a vision for future model benchmarking tools and methods.

The Model Benchmarking Task Team is co-led by Birgit Hassler (DLR, Germany), Forrest Hoffman (ORNL, USA) and Ranjini Swaminathan (University of Reading, UK). Full Task Team membership is [available on their website](#).

Spotlight on... Rapid Evaluation Framework

The CMIP Panel approved the concept for a new Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF) on 18 June 2024, proposed by the [Model Benchmarking Task Team](#), for the [CMIP Assessment Fast Track](#) focused on supporting the next IPCC Assessment Report 7 (AR7) cycle.

The REF is a new framework which will allow for model simulations to be rapidly evaluated by a range of existing diagnostics as the data is uploaded to ESGF. It is designed to be open source and modular, available via ESGF but also in containerised form. Evaluating climate models in this way allows for modelling centres to validate their model and allows users to assess and investigate the CMIP data. Overall, this leads to a better scientific understanding of the data that is being produced for CMIP and increases the integrity of its associated science.

Testing and development

Over this past year the members of the Model Benchmarking Task Team, working with a dedicated delivery team, resourced by the US Department of Energy and the European Space Agency, along with contributions from the ESMValTool, ILAMB, IOMB, CMEC and PMP benchmarking packages, have developed and tested the REF interaction with external services (see Figure 4).

This included running a hybrid hackathon, hosted by the UK Met Office in March 2025, where the REF was tested by Earth System and high-resolution modellers.

Scientific requirements at the observation-modelling interface were raised, including requirements, location and use of uncertainty metadata and advancements in complex citation objects.

Following the hackathon, there was refinement of various components including removal of two of the diagnostics. A Beta release was launched in May for testing by the community on Github. Members of the delivery team have also met several times with members of the IPCC Task Group on Data Support for Climate Change Assessments (TG-Data) with feedback provided on the REF's provenance template, helping to ensure it will be compatible with the needs of IPCC authors.

All reference datasets being used for the AFT diagnostics in the REF have been through the obs4MIPs dataset proposal review process conducted by the obs4MIPs steering panel. The decision was taken, in consultation with obs4MIPs Steering Panel, to initially publish the datasets on a temporary dedicated project on the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) called obs4REF to prove concept for a number of advancements required in addition to the ODS2.5 specification and to test 'CMOR-like' reference dataset preparation and validation.

Figure 4: Lewis et al. (2025) REF key services and interactions with external services including ESGF.

The REF will also be an early adopter of the new CVs infrastructure in order to be ready for the early CMIP7 datasets. Once obs4MIPs is successfully operational on next generation of ESGF (ESGF NG), the REF will transition to reference dataset ingest from obs4MIPs.

Integrating the REF onto the next generation of ESGF

The delivery team, which includes representatives from two ESGF nodes; ORNL and CEDA; are now working with members of the CMIP7 CVs Task Team to prepare the REF for inclusion in the next generation of ESGF (ESGF-NG) which adopts a centralised model, with two search nodes, one in the US and one in Europe each hosted on public cloud, synchronised together using a new event-driven architecture. ESGF will provide the users of the REF with efficient access to observational data prepared for comparison with model output, direct access to model output as soon as it is published, a platform for computing the evaluation and analysis, and a website for display and distribution of REF output.

This improves the availability of, and global access to, evaluated simulations as well as supporting community efforts to reduce the carbon footprint.

2.4 Model Documentation Task Team

The Model Documentation Task Team has continued to work towards enabling the collection and storage of model documentation, and other related documentation, which are most important to the CMIP community. The aim is to build on the model documentation provided for CMIP6, by ensuring full coverage across models, and improved consistency with related aspects of CMIP infrastructure, such as the controlled vocabularies.

In the previous period the concept of “Essential Model Documentation” (EMD) was outlined, and a first draft was presented to the CMIP panel for comment in summer 2024. Completion of EMD by modelling centres will allow it to be stored in the CMIP7 controlled vocabularies. From there it can be further disseminated, and act as a single source of truth on model details (enabling more effective metadata QA/QC). A survey was circulated which aimed to capture whether MIPs and modelling centres found the level of detail captured by the EMD specification appropriate, and whether there were any important model details not captured. Feedback was received which was generally positive, however some clarifications and additions were suggested. These, as well as the panel comments received, were then addressed.

Early in 2025 a decision request was formulated which included the first version of the EMD specification to be released, as well as a plan for its implementation. This included the following elements;

- A web collection tool to collect and check values and generate an issue to be reviewed
- Content stored in GitHub in JSON-LD files, in the same place as experiment registration, source IDs etc.
- Working with CVs Task Team to ensure that the vocabularies required for EMD are captured and stored
- Including EMD creation as part of the model registration process (meaning EMD needs to be submitted before data can be published to ESGF)

This decision request was put to both the WIP and CMIP Panel, and was approved in February 2025 (decision ID [62](#)). The EMD contents were subsequently finalised and [released on Zenodo](#). Since then, the focus has been on the EMD’s implementation.

In parallel, the Task Team has devoted some time to considering other aspects of CMIP documentation not directly related to the model details. This includes machine and performance, experiments, conformance, ensembles, tuning, and forcings and inputs.

The Task Team will create a document describing these different sources of information and identifying those which can be collected and stored with the same infrastructure as the EMD, and those which require a separate solution. The need for improved entry level documentation was also identified. This work is being developed via a Fresh Eyes Project.

The Model Documentation Task Team was co-led by David Hassell (NCAS, UK) and Guillaume Levavasseur (IPSL, France). After the finalisation of the EMD specification, Guillaume Levavasseur stepped down from the co-lead role to focus on CV-related activities, and following a call for nominations from Task Team members, Charlotte Pascoe (NCAS, UK) filled the second co-lead position. Full Task Team membership is [available on their website](#).

2.5 Strategic Ensemble Design Task Team

Following their intensive activity developing the CMIP7 AFT experiment selection recommendation, the Strategic Ensemble Design (SED) Task Team co-leads, Isla Simpson (NCAR, USA) and Ben Sanderson (CICERO, Norway) strongly supported the development of the CMIP7 AFT and discussion of the potential for model sub-sampling sections of the CMIP7 Overview Paper (Dunne et al., 2025).

Further the Task Team identified and conducted initial discussions on the following emerging questions:

1. Emissions driven strategy and Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), including surveying the CMIP modelling centres on the expected BECCS representation in CMIP7 models (p12–28, [O'Rourke, 2024](#)).
2. Downstream model selection - potential for coordinated strategies to support downstream activities such as CORDEX, ISIMIP and ISMIP7.
3. Emissions driven scenarios and AFT scenario selection.

These topics were discussed in a Task Team meeting in September 2024 and further in spin off small group discussions. In November 2024, the SED Task Team co-leads proposed to the CMIP Panel that the Task Team could be wound down having fulfilled its objectives and this was approved by CMIP Core Panel in December 2024 ([decision ID 58](#)). The spin off discussions have been integrated into other activities; BECCS is being addressed within a reinvigorated CDRMIP, a virtual [Streamlining Model Selection](#) workshop took place in February 2025 (see section 4.1 for more details) with follow up sessions planned for during the EU project ESM2025 Final Event and CMIP Community Workshop, and the chairs of the CMIP Panel and ScenarioMIP remain in close contact regarding the finalisation and potential running order of scenarios and extensions for the AFT.

The CMIP Panel would like to thank the SED Task Team co-leads and all members for playing a pivotal role in the initial selection and development of the Assessment Fast Track experiments, working both within the team itself and with the wider CMIP community.

The Strategic Ensemble Design Task Team was co-led by Isla Simpson (NCAR, USA) and Ben Sanderson (CICERO, Norway). Full Task Team membership is [available on their website](#).

2.6 Energy Consumption and Carbon Footprint

The Energy Consumption and Carbon Footprint Task Team was formed in May 2025. The team was set up by the CMIP Panel to evaluate the carbon footprint of CMIP activities, including energy usage from model experiments, data storage and replication, and administrative activities such as conferences and online meetings.

The Task Team has held their kick-off meeting, during which the members debated the merits of the initial aims and objectives and decided to focus initially on providing a user-guide with instructions for the modelling centres, explaining what information the Task Team needs to measure for a multi-site model comparison of energy consumption. The user-guide will focus on metrics with and without model outputs, thereby collecting data relevant to footprint analysis. These guidelines will build on previous work lead by the team at Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BCS) based on CMIP6 activities, with publication slated for October 2025.

The Task Team has also initiated contact with an FEOC project analysing data usage. As the majority of CMIP data is published to the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF), any statistics on publication, downloads and use of CMIP data from the ESGF Metagrid will be valuable for footprint analysis.

Additionally, the Task Team has worked actively to introduce some tasks into a European project proposal, which will support European CMIP activities. The new tasks included in the project will provide support to the Task Team and enable rapid interaction between project partners and the Task Team.

The Energy Consumption and Carbon Footprint Task Team currently has one co-lead, Mario Acosta (BCS, Spain), with a second co-lead to be confirmed later in 2025. Further information and the complete Task Team membership are [available on their website](#).

2.7 Controlled Vocabularies

The controlled vocabularies are central to the CMIP infrastructure, ensuring uniformity in the description of datasets across all models, and are used in the construction of file naming and directory repository structures (DRS) used for model outputs. The aim of the Task Team is to generate a registry of ‘controlled terms’ which describe all descriptive facets for climate modelling (used by CMIP, and beyond). These allow us to better describe our datasets, provide provenance information, and avoid the duplication of work in creation and management of terms and search facets.

The CVs underpin the core of many CMIP activities, the Task Team are regularly working together with members from ESGF, the Model Documentation Task Team, and the Data Request Task Team to implement the CVs, the EMD, and a Variable Registry.

Over the past year, the Task Team has worked on creating a reusable, human-readable, linked framework for the CVs structure in GitHub. This allows for community contributions, ensuring the correct attributions are given for the development work, and sufficient error checking and review. Significant work has also gone into the documentation of the CVs, both through readme descriptions and attractive web views. These will be available for the community in mid to late 2025.

Additionally, many of the steps following on from user registration of a new CV through to its publication have been automated, reducing the burden on the Task Team and the wider CMIP Community.

To advance their work, the CVs Task Team met for three days in Paris in May 2025, hosted by IPSL. During the workshop, the members discussed the list of tasks required over the coming months, and identified any roadblocks which might hinder their work. Throughout the course of the meeting, the Task Team agreed consistent naming of the keys to be used in the CVs JSON schema, shared updates and calibrated on the current work of ESGVOC and CVs development, and began the relevant grids and facets needed for EMD to the CVs. Finally, the meeting hosted a discussion on user workflows and user interaction with the planned Variable Registry alongside members of the Data Request Task Team.

The Controlled Vocabularies Task Team is co-led by Karl Taylor (PCMDI /LLNL, US) and Laurent Troussellier (IPSL, France), with the purpose of developing, designing and implementing an improved framework for recording and managing vocabularies that can serve CMIP and related WGCM and ESMO activities.

2.8 Climate Data Node Operations Team

CDNOT was originally set up as a working group under the auspices of the WCRP/WGCM to administer data nodes within the [Earth System Grid Federation \(ESGF\)](#) and conduct a series of data challenges to test node infrastructure capabilities ahead of CMIP6. Since January 2025, it has benefited from the secretariat support of the CMIP IPO and as a Task Team reports to the WIP.

The primary role of CDNOT is the coordination of node managers to ensure consistency in the publication and replication of CMIP data and climate datasets of relevance to the community (e.g. CORDEX). The CMIP IPO administers a dedicated CDNOT mailing list and helps the Task Team co-leads organise monthly meetings where the co-leads update node managers on changes to the ESGF software used for publication and replication and any architecture changes to ESGF Metagrid that will affect node operations. In turn, the managers can share information about problems they are having and receive advice.

In the last six months the CDNOT community has met four times, with the focus being the change from ESGF 1.0 to 1.5 and following that the change from 1.5 to NG (Next Generation) completion expected by September 2025. Both updates require node managers to instigate important changes to their software stack to ensure continued operation.

Another important activity has been the ESGF Node Survey organised by CMIP IPO with input from the Task Team co-leads and CORDEX team. The survey completed in April 2025 provided important information on the state of the federation including operational nodes, node resources, capability and storage capacity for CMIP and CORDEX activities. Feedback from the survey participants to the CDNOT Task Team although expressing satisfaction with CDNOT, emphasised improvements to engagement and communication.

This has prompted discussion within CDNOT on re-introducing a second online meeting per month to accommodate node managers in Asia and Oceania, where engagement has been lacking. Another suggestion from the community is to establish a dedicated channel on ESGF Slack for CDNOT that could share meeting notes and essential information for node managers and prompt community engagement. As the ESGF Slack is the principal communication source for ESGF technical matters, this would allow nodes outside of the current meeting time-zones to interact. Both options will be explored after ESGF-NG is operational.

CDNOT has two co-leads, Sasha Ames (LLNL, USA) and Katharina Berger (DKRZ, Germany). Further information on the Task Team and the membership can be found on the [dedicated website](#).

2.9 Quality Control / Quality Assessment Working Group

Following an ESGF face to face meeting in October 2024, the need for a working group on the quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) of WCRP data emerged. A working group was formed which brought together ESGF developers, the WIP, and stakeholders such as the REF developers and the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S). One major aim is to exploit the opportunity presented by parallel initiatives, such as a C3S contract which is providing an IPSL-led group funding to update the CMIP6 quality control infrastructure for C3S use. The group also seeks coordination with other working groups or task teams as required, including the Controlled Vocabularies Task Team, as interfacing with the CVs is a key requirement of effective QC.

The main priority of the group is to coordinate the development of minimum viable QC infrastructure for CMIP7. The aim, following consideration of the available options, is for the ESGF publisher to be able to use the modular [QC framework being built at IPSL](#). The exact QC checks used by the publisher need to balance the requirements of downstream infrastructure such as the REF with the compute load on ESGF nodes during the publication process, and the final configuration is still under discussion. Once defined, WIP approval for the ESGF publisher QC configuration will be sought.

A second objective is to ensure that any software developed has buy-in from the community, and can serve a wide range of needs. Additional 'contexts' can be defined in the framework to extend or change the priority of the checks for different situations. The CORDEX community is now also engaged in the project.

The working group is co-led by Guillaume Levavasseur (IPSL, France) and Sasha Aimes (LLNL, USA). Some details of the working group and current membership are [provided on the website](#).

2.10 Fresh Eyes on CMIP

Fresh Eyes on CMIP is working group integrating the voices of early career researchers (ECRs), scientists and practitioners in CMIP. Researchers, scientists and practitioners early in their career provide a unique insight into climate science. Coming into the system more recently enables ECRs to have a fresh perspective on CMIP. ECRs regularly undertake the often time-consuming task of generating, downloading, processing, and analysing data from CMIP and as such, have a unique, working insight into the successes and flaws of CMIP phases. Fresh Eyes on CMIP sits alongside the CMIP7 Task Teams.

Over the past year, **Fresh Eyes has evolved into a new structure**, reflecting lessons learned during their first year of work. The new structure was developed in collaboration with the co-leads, Douglas Rao and Julia Mindlin, CMIP Panel co-chairs, Helene Hewitt and John Dunne, and the CMIP IPO. The new structure retains many of the features of the original set-up, but allows for a more open membership to Fresh Eyes, members to commit to projects based on their own interests and time commitments, and more freedom for members of Fresh Eyes, the Task Teams, and CMIP Governance to propose projects. In the old structure, Fresh Eyes members were sorted into existing subgroups and invited to devise their own workplan.

In many cases, this structure facilitated the development of a number of exciting projects. However, it was reported that some Fresh Eyes members wished to engage with a lower level of commitment. Additionally, some subgroups struggled to devise a project with limited engagement from their ‘twinned’ CMIP7 Task Teams, while some engaged members had new project ideas which they could not find a home for in the old structure. In the new structure, there are two streams of Fresh Eyes members: all members join the Fresh Eyes Directory, while those who wish to engage and collaborate more closely can also sign-up for the Fresh Eyes Projects stream.

Over the past year, many exciting and innovative projects have been developed by the Fresh Eyes subgroups including:

1. Assessing the impact and use of CMIP data
2. Testing Forcing datasets ready for CMIP7
3. Introduction to CMIP for first timers (‘Entry Level Documentation’)
4. Responsible use of CMIP data
5. Data analysis tools and recipes repository
6. Model evaluation requirements and recommendations

A Fresh Eyes Platform has also been created in GitHub, to allow for improved engagement and communication across Fresh Eyes members, in addition to being a hub where resources, job opportunities, and social interactions can be shared. Following a test period, all Fresh Eyes members will be invited to join the Platform in July 2025.

On 21 May 2025, Fresh Eyes held the inaugural **Fresh Eyes Workshop: Fresh Eyes on CMIP Around the World**. The day was a huge success, starting in an Asia and Oceania hub, shifting after eight hours to the Europe and Africa hub, and finishing almost 22 hours later in our Americas hub. During the day, the workshop welcomed over 185 participants and heard contributions from 36 different CMIP community members from across the world. All of the recordings from the day and slides from our speakers are available on the **event website**.

Fresh Eyes members have been active in the CMIP and broad WCRP community. Members of Fresh Eyes on CMIP have been organizing regular scientific sessions around model uncertainty during AGU and EGU annual meetings. Additionally, Active Fresh Eyes members are now emerging as leaders in various WCRP activities - Monica Morrison co-leads the joint task team with RIfS on Responsible Use of CMIP data, Timothy Lam is now the science officer at RIfS International Project Office, and Douglas Rao co-leads the new ESMO Working Group on Observations for Researching Climate (WGORC).

3 CMIP Scientific Highlights

The data from existing CMIP phases continues to be heavily used throughout the community. CMIP6 data publication began in 2019 and much of the data publication was completed in 2022. Below are selected highlights by the CMIP IPO's Science and Communications Officer, from high-impact science journals which have made use of the CMIP data.

3.1 Atlantic overturning inferred from air-sea heat fluxes indicates no decline since the 1960s

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) is crucial for global ocean carbon and heat uptake and determines large-scale weather and climate around the North Atlantic. Despite its importance, understanding its past changes and estimating how climate change might impact the AMOC remain major open questions in climate science. Many previous studies of historical changes in AMOC have used proxies, particularly sea surface temperature anomalies. In this study, Terhaar et al., use CMIP6 data to show that these temperature anomalies cannot robustly reconstruct the AMOC.

In their paper, the authors show that air-sea heat flux anomalies north of any given latitude in the North Atlantic between 26.5°N and 50°N are tightly linked to the AMOC anomaly at that latitude on decadal and centennial timescales. They show that these anomalies are strongly linked to the AMOC through energy conservation. The same result is not true on annual timescales, where these anomalies are instead likely altered predominantly by atmospheric variability.

Terhaar et al., conclude, by using the observation-based estimates of air-sea heat flux in the North Atlantic that “the decadal averaged AMOC at 26.5°N has not weakened from 1963 to 2017 although substantial variability exists at all latitudes.”

This paper was mentioned 76 news stories by 67 outlets around the world and has an Altmetric score of 1255.

Figure 5: The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) anomalies are calculated at 26.5°N for 24 climate models individually with respect to a linear trend over the time period in the pre-industrial AMOC simulations of each model that corresponds to the time period in the historical simulations. The subpolar gyre sea surface temperature (SPG SST) anomalies following Caesar et al. 34 are calculated with respect to a linear trend over the time period in the pre-industrial AMOC simulations of each model that corresponds to the time period in the historical simulations. Blue dots indicate averages of the respective anomalies from a 1850 to 2016, and from 2017 to 2100 under b SSP1–2.6 and c SSP5–8.5. Orange dots indicate decadal averages of the anomalies from a the 1850s to the 2010s, and from b, c the 2020s to the 2090s. Green dots show annual averaged anomalies from a 1850 to 2016, and b, c from 2017 to 2100. Only the relationship for overall averages in (a) is not statistically significant. Figure and caption from Terhaar et al., 2025.

Terhaar, J., Vogt, L. & Foukal, N.P. Atlantic overturning inferred from air-sea heat fluxes indicates no decline since the 1960s. *Nature Communications*, 16, 222 (2025). doi: [10.1038/s41467-024-55297-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-55297-5)

3.2 A year above 1.5 °C signals that Earth is most probably within the 20-year period that will reach the Paris Agreement limit

Following the announcement that 2024 was the first year where the year-averaged temperature exceeded 1.5°C, this paper confirmed that, without intense climate mitigation, the first year above 1.5°C occurs within the first 20-year period with 1.5°C average warming. This is a key conclusion as the Paris Agreement, a legal treaty agreed by 195 Parties at COP21, aims to keep the global average temperature under 1.5°C. Assessing when this target is breached is difficult, due to the non-linear behaviour of temperature. The IPCC defined a series of Global Warming Levels (GWLs) in its sixth Assessment Report (AR6), such that exceeding the 1.5°C GWL happens when the temperature during the midpoint of a 20-year period is 1.5°C higher than pre-industrial period.

In this paper, the authors used CMIP6 data alongside observations to analyse GWLs which have already been reached (namely 0.6°C, 0.7°C, 0.8°C, 0.9°C, and 1.0°C) and found that the first calendar year where the global average temperature breached these temperatures consistently fell within the first 20-year period where the same average temperature was breached. Further, by looking at the CMIP6 scenarios, Bevacqua et al., found that, without intense climate mitigation, the first calendar year at 1.5°C is virtually certain (probability of ~99%) to fall in the 20-year period that reaches the 1.5°C warming level. Even in scenarios with stringent near-term emission reductions (SSP1.2.6 and SSP1-1.9), the probability still reaches around 75%.

The paper closes with a call to action for climate mitigation and adaptation given this early warning that we have probably already entered a 20-year period at 1.5°C warming.

This paper was popular in the media, with an Altmetric score of 1285 and was mentioned in 145 news stories from 117 outlets.

a Lag of first warm year from entry time in 20-yr period

b Lag of first 1.5°C year from entry time in 20-yr period

Figure 6: a, The time lag is denoted by Δt , with positive values implying that the first year above a warming level occurred within the 20-year period reaching the same warming level (vertical light orange band). The blue dots indicate different observational datasets. The box plots (showing median and interquartile range) are derived from models under a moderate emissions scenario SSP2-4.5 (black whiskers extend to the most extreme data points within 1.5 times the interquartile range from the box). b, The same as the box plot in a but for 1.5 °C warming under different emission scenarios (here, grey whiskers display the full range if it exceeds black whiskers). The number of models employed (those compatible with observed recent warming trends²⁰) is shown in brackets. The fraction of simulations that fall in the shaded area is also provided. Figure and caption from Bevacqua et al., 2025.

Bevacqua, E., Schleussner, CF. & Zscheischler, J. A year above 1.5 °C signals that Earth is most probably within the 20-year period that will reach the Paris Agreement limit. *Nature Climate Change*, 15, 262–265 (2025). doi: [10.1038/s41558-025-02246-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-025-02246-9).

3.3 Highest ocean heat in four centuries places Great Barrier Reef in danger

Mass coral bleaching in the Great Barrier Reef in the past decade was driven by high Sea Surface Temperatures (SSTs). In this paper, Henley et al. reconstruct SSTs from geochemical records in the corals themselves.

Using this reconstruction, the authors are able to show that the years 2024, 2017, and 2020 were the warmest in the past 400 year, with 2016, 2004, and 2022 the next three warmest. The authors attribute this warming to human influence on the climate system using CMIP data.

The authors conclude that these findings are of great concern to the longevity of the Great Barrier Reef, given the significant warming that is anticipated to happen by the end of the century. Coral reefs require 10–20 years to recover from severe mass bleaching, therefore with such events increasing in frequency, it is unlikely reefs will have time to fully recover between events.

Figure 7: Ranked January–March SSTAs for 1618–2024 relative to 1961–90 (coloured circles) from the best-estimate (highest skill, full coral network) reconstruction (1618–1899) and instrumental (ERSSTv5) data (1900–2024). The year is indicated by the colour of the filled circles. The 5th–95th-percentile uncertainty bounds of the pre-1900 reconstructed SSTAs are shown by small grey dots. The year labels indicate the warmest six years on record, five of which were mass coral bleaching years on the GBR. The pink (upper) dashed line indicates the 95th-percentile uncertainty bound of the maximum pre-1900 reconstructed SSTA; the red (lower) dashed line indicates the 90th-percentile limit. Figure and caption from Henley et al., 2024.

Henley, B.J., McGregor, H.V., King, A.D. et al. Highest ocean heat in four centuries places Great Barrier Reef in danger. *Nature*, 632, 320–326 (2024). doi: [10.1038/s41586-024-07672-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07672-x).

3.4 Increasing boreal fires reduce future global warming and sea ice loss

Biomass burning emissions from boreal forests have been increasing dramatically for the past two decades and are expected to continue to increase. However, CMIP6-era models have no active fire component and instead prescribe biomass burning emissions. In CMIP6, these emissions from boreal forests were prescribed with an unrealistic near-zero trend. In this paper, Blanchard-Wrigglesworth et al., investigate if this difference in observed and modelled emissions impacts climate trends by running CESM2 with standard CMIP6 forcings, but increasing boreal biomass burning emissions, based on the observed emissions.

The authors find that this increase in biomass burning emissions reduces global warming by 12% and Arctic warming by 38% compared with using the CMIP6 forcing, because of a reduction in surface shortwave flux over the Northern Hemisphere. The changes lead to a slowdown in Arctic sea ice loss, while tropical precipitation shifts southward.

The authors conclude that these results highlight the importance of having realistic boreal biomass burning emissions in climate models and specifically that CMIP7 should consider projections of future boreal biomass burning emissions in 21st century scenarios.

Figure 8: Future warming rates under increased future boreal fires. (A) Evolution of global mean surface temperature in BorealFire (red) and CEM2-LE (black), with individual members shown as thin lines and the ensemble mean indicated by the thick line. The BorealFire ensemble mean line is highlighted with a black border during years when its difference with the CEM2-LE ensemble mean is greater than the CEM2-LE ensemble SE. (B) As in (A), but for Arctic temperature (70°N to 90°N). Linear temperature trend over 2015–2060 in °C per decade in (C) BorealFire, (D) CEM2-LE, and (E) the difference between the two. Regions where the difference in trends is greater than the CEM2-LE ensemble SE are stippled. From Blanchard-Wrigglesworth et al., 2025

Blanchard-Wrigglesworth, E., DeRepentigny, P., Frierson, D. M. W.. Increasing boreal fires reduce future global warming and sea ice loss. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science U.S.A.*, 122 (23) e2424614122 (2025). doi: [10.1073/pnas.2424614122](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2424614122)

4 Events and engagement

4.1 Events

Pathway to Regular and Sustained Delivery of Climate Forcing Datasets

Thirty in-person, and more than 40 online participants met between 28 and 31 October 2024 to review the current provision model and delivery of the CMIP7 DECK forcings suite, discuss the key challenges, hear from users and funders of the data, co-create a range of practical implementation options, develop the vision and generate concrete actions towards regular and sustained climate forcings dataset delivery. The **four-day workshop** was co-organised by the CMIP Climate Forcings Task Team, ECMWF Copernicus Climate Services, ESA Climate and Long Term Action Division and the CMIP International Project Office. Huge thanks to ECMWF who kindly hosted the workshop at their UK site in Reading, and to ESA for hosting the meeting dinner.

The first two days of the workshop focused on the progress towards delivery of the CMIP7 DECK forcings suite to support the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track. Each dataset provider outlined the status of their dataset, highlighted any critical issues, key data dependencies, and discussed protocol development, understanding of uncertainties, and importantly the many exciting science questions remaining.

To launch the call for modelling centre feedback on the DECK Forcings, the Forcings Task Team held an open community drop-in session on Day 2 of the workshop to encourage users to test the **available datasets** and provide feedback via **GitHub**. Members of the scenarios community also provided update on the CMIP7 scenario development, plans for harmonisation and challenges to be addressed.

On Day 3 the focus pivoted to looking beyond the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track and CMIP to a sustained mode delivery for forcings dataset with regular updates. A users panel provided insight into the surprising breadth of users and potential users of forcings data. Additionally, funders panel highlighted the need to raise the visibility of the impact of the forcings data, and the funding and resource gaps that may limit providers from moving to a sustained mode delivery. An afternoon breakout session allowed for some further in-depth discussion on sustained mode challenges beyond funding including ensuring adequate recognition for providers, data provenance issues, potential for prototype/beta products, and documentation needs.

Carlo Buontempo, C3S Director, brought the workshop to a close on Day 4 by summarising a set of outline actions across short, medium and longer timescales providing a transitional pathway to sustained delivery of climate forcing data to serve a wider user community. The Forcings Task Team, supported by the CMIP Panel and CMIP IPO, have continued to work to implement the workshop outcomes. Slides and recordings from the workshop are available on the [workshop webpage](#).

Rapid Evaluation Framework Hackathon

Between 10th–13th March 2025, over 90 participants from around the world gathered to co-develop the [Rapid Evaluation Framework](#) at a [dedicated 4-day hybrid hackathon](#) hosted by the Met Office in Exeter, UK.

Four separate workstreams were run in parallel, targeting different aspects of the REF development: Metrics development, Infrastructure, Observation data products, and Documentation. The Model Benchmarking Task Team co-leads and the REF development team members shared updates on the progress of the REF across each workstream and engaged with experts and community members in multiple open sessions throughout the week. Software development sessions and hands-on training for running the REF were also provided by members of the development team.

The four-day event showcased the REF development activities to the community as well as providing important scientific, technical and operational feedback to the REF development team. This was particularly important for ensuring the REF is positioned at the forefront of piloting advancements in complex citations. Helpful input on complex citations was provided by representatives from the IPCC's Task Group on Data Support for Climate Change Assessments. Important suggestions for strengthening the observation-modelling interface were made including handling observational uncertainties. Many of the points raised were also made in the recently published report by the Climate Modelling User Group.

Overall, the Hackathon significantly advanced REF development, identified gaps in its planned structure, and provided valuable input from the community on how to grow the REF more broadly for model evaluation. Suggestions for future benchmarking development featured including a wider array of simulations, observational datasets, and metrics.

Helene Hewitt, co-chair of the CMIP Panel welcomed the progress made by those participating in person and online,

“ The Rapid Evaluation Framework is a potential game changer for users of CMIP data. The CMIP panel wants to extend its thanks to the model benchmarking task team, hackathon participants, and the funding bodies especially ESA and DoE for their contributions. ”

Streamlining Model Selection workshop

An ongoing challenge for climate data users is the time taken between the global climate simulations and the provision of data relevant to end users. CMIP, together with colleagues in [CORDEX](#), [ISMIP](#), [ISMIP7](#), [GlacierMIP](#) and others, identified the need for a collaborative effort to streamline this process. To progress towards this shared goal, a collaborative, virtual workshop [Streamlining Model Selection](#) was held on 5 February 2025.

The workshop opened with a summary of the objectives (Christian Stepanek, DWD) and an example of challenges faced by users under the current framework (Sven Kotlarski, Meteo Swiss) before four examples of current best practice in model selection were shared: EURO-CORDEX for CMIP6 (Stefan Sobolowski, University of Bergen), CORDEX-Australia for CMIP6 (Michael Grose, CSIRO), model selection for regional climate modelling downscaling in ISMIP6 (Céline Agosta, LSCE/IPSL), and the ISMIP approach (Lisa Novak, PIK Potsdam).

The introductory presentations were followed by two breakout sessions. The first focused on scientific challenges within the problem, such as metrics and frameworks for model selection, how model development impacts selection, and uncertainty questions within the selection problem. The second breakout session considered non-scientific challenges, such as timelines of data availability, data infrastructure, and competing requirements.

Looking ahead, a follow up workshop is being held during the ESM2025 General Assembly in Toulouse in October 2025. This workshop will be a focused practical discussion between the downstream activities and modelling centre representatives on streamlining the model selection approaches and process for the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track anticipated to be available on the timeline required.

EGU25

The European Geophysical Union's General Assembly in 2025 (EGU24) took place in Vienna in April. EGU25 welcomed over 18,500 in-person attendees from 120 countries with over 2000 people also joining online. The IPO was delighted to host an extended Townhall during the week and two informal lightning talks.

The Townhall – [An update on CMIP7: forcings, data request, the REF and more](#) – included an update on the plans for CMIP7 and the Assessment Fast Track, an overview of the Data Request development with insights from three of the thematic author teams, a summary of the Rapid Evaluation Framework strategic plan and development work, and a presentation outlining the work of the Forcings Task Team in curating the CMIP7 DECK forcings suite and plans for a future sustained mode. After a short break, The Townhall also featured an expo on the work of the Fresh Eyes on CMIP community. Seven of the active projects presented their latest work, which spurred a lot of discussion among attendees. Full Townhall slides can be [accessed from the Zenodo website](#).

Fresh Eyes on CMIP Around the World

The Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group and CMIP Panel co-chairs proposed and organised an inaugural [Fresh Eyes workshop: Fresh Eyes on CMIP Around the World](#) on 21 May 2025. This was to be a marathon virtual day, bringing together the Fresh Eyes community alongside CMIP Panel and Task Team members and the wider CMIP community.

The day combined three regional hubs, each overlapping to bring together our global membership. Kicking off the workshop, the Asia and Oceania hub began at 01:45 UTC, welcoming a number of scientific presentations, Fresh Eyes Projects updates, a Panel discussion, and virtual networking sessions featuring a Science for Policy game developed by Simon Clarke (EGU). At 07:00 UTC a two-hour handover period began, where both the Asia and Oceania hub members were online alongside the Europe and Africa hub members logging on for the first time. The structure of each hub remained the same, and the handover period between the Europe and Africa hub to the Americas hub started at 14:00 UTC, before the workshop concluded at 21:30 UTC, almost 21 hours after it first started.

The day was a huge success! During the day, the workshop welcomed over 185 participants and heard contributions from 36 different CMIP community members from across the world All of the recordings from the day and slides from our speakers are [available on the event website](#).

LPS25

Held every three years, ESA's Living Planet Symposia are among the world's premier events on Earth observation. The symposia continue to expand in both size and scope. With the climate crisis intensifying, the [Living Planet Symposium 2025 \(LPS25\)](#) emphasised transitioning from 'observation to climate action and sustainability for Earth'. In 2025, the event was held between 22 and 27 June in Vienna, Austria.

CMIP had a strong presence at LPS25, with ESA as the host of the CMIP IPO. Three members of the CMIP IPO attended the meeting, alongside CMIP Panel co-chair, Helene Hewitt. CMIP chaired a session alongside the ESMO IPO titled 'Advances at the observation-modelling interface', which featured presentations on the role of observations in climate forcings, observational requirements for model benchmarking, and emerging technologies in Earth system modelling. In addition to this session, the CMIP IPO also organised and facilitated two Agora sessions. The first featured a panel discussion on how to delivery sustained mode climate forcings and particularly focussed on the role of Earth observations within that problem. The second Agora continued to focus on the critical role of Earth Observations within the modelling community, this time putting the spotlight on climate model evaluation and benchmarking.

Presentations during the Agora provided an overview of the Rapid Evaluation Framework, observation requirements of model evaluation, how to participate in community model diagnostics and performance metric packages, and finally Dóra Hegedüs gave a demonstration on how to get observational datasets 'REF-ready'.

Alongside the CMIP sessions and Agoras, the CMIP and ESMO IPOs and WCRP Secretariat also hosted daily drop-in sessions alongside our activity members., boosting our engagement across the conference significantly.

Finally, the conference featured a number of plenary panel discussions on cross-cutting themes. One of these discussions, titled 'The global crisis and Earth action: understanding our planet', featured Helene Hewitt. The discussion explored how we understand our planet using climate models and observations. The panellists discussed the role of climate forcings, Earth observations, and high-resolution modelling in addition to sharing their insights from their work in global collaborations, including in the IPCC, WCRP, GCOS, and the European Commission's Joint Research Centre.

CMIP Seminars

Science is at the heart of CMIP. To promote the breadth of excellent science being done that utilises CMIP data, [a monthly seminar series](#) was launched in March 2024, with the first session held on 24 April 2024. Seminars are held on the final Wednesday of each month at alternating times of 08:00 UTC and 16:00 UTC to allow for presenters and audience members across all time zones. Each seminar features three speakers and allows time for both presentations and questions. Many of the presentations are [uploaded to YouTube](#) afterwards, to allow for anyone to watch and learn about science which makes use of CMIP data. The seminars have proved to be very popular, with over 690 people registered to receive joining details.

4.2 Engagement

The CMIP community regularly engages with many different partners and organisations, within and beyond the WCRP landscape, across the modelling multiverse, observational community, downstream activities, climate services, and funders at all levels. Below are a few examples of these engagements.

ScenarioMIP

The CMIP Panel co-chairs and IPO have worked closely with the ScenarioMIP leadership over the past year as they have finalised development of the CMIP7 scenarios. This included supporting a [formal endorsement of the process and proposed scenarios](#) for CMIP7 from the WCRP Joint Scientific Committee, confirmed in February 2025. Regular dialogue has continued between CMIP and ScenarioMIP as they refine the scenario selection in light of community review of their initial proposal (van Vuuren et al., 2025) and to collaboratively work, together with the CMIP Forcings Task Team, towards an aligned delivery timeline to facilitate scenario projections.

Downstream activities

Together with ScenarioMIP, CMIP has also been working closely with downstream activities such as the WCRP Coordinated Regional Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX), Inter-Sectoral Impacts MIP (ISIMIP) and Ice Sheet MIP (ISMIP7) to try to facilitate their use of CMIP7 AFT to deliver on the AR7 timeline.

This has included co-organisation of the [Streamlining Model Selection](#), held online on 5th February 2025, planning a follow up hybrid event [Model selection – supporting downstream activities use of CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track](#). The group has developed potential advice for modelling centres for a scenarios running order where the ‘high’ and ‘very low with low overshoot’ scenarios would be run first to increase the time available for the downstream activities to complete their own simulations.

CEOS WG–Climate and WG–CapD

Together with ESMO, CMIP has working to strengthen the observation–modelling interface. An invited presentation was given by representatives from ESMO SSG, WGORC and CMIP IPO in February to the joint CEOS/CGMS Working Group on Climate (WGClimate) and Greenhouse Gas Task Team (GHG-TT) which led to the establishment of regular joint meetings between ESMO WGORC and CEOS WGClimate. A further presentation invitation was extended by the CEOS Working Group on Capacity Building and Data Democracy who were particularly interested in what could be done to strengthen the use of observations in model evaluation. Ideas were put forward for a pilot scheme for the REF, to establish dedicated observation–modelling interface champions and are under consideration. The Model Benchmarking Task Team will work with WGORC, who is leading on ESMO interaction with CEOS WGClimate, to progress this over the next year.

Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP)

CMIP is a project of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) providing climate projections to understand past, present, and future climate changes. CMIP and its associated data infrastructure have become essential to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and other international and national climate assessments.

 [CMIP – Coupled Model Intercomparison Project](#)

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 [wcrp-cmip.org](#)

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